

Chemical Examination of the Flowers of *Peltophorum inermi* Roxb.

I. P. Varshney and N. K. Dube

The flowers of *Peltophorum inermi* Roxb. on alcohol extraction and subsequent treatment gave a number of crystalline products. Two of the products have been identified as β -sitosterol and lupeol.

Peltophorum inermi Roxb. belongs to the family Leguminosae, sub-family Caesalpiniaceae and is a large sized tree. A review of the literature showed that the flowers of this plant contain¹ an unidentified colourless compound m.p. 146–47° and the bark has been reported to contain² (+) leucocynidin (5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxy-flavin-3,4-diol) but there is no report of the existence of any saponin (free) or saponin in the flowers and bark.

The flowers of this plant were collected from the trees found in the city of Indore. The air dried powdered flowers were exhausted with alcohol, which on concentration gave a dark coloured gummy mass. This on extraction with (i) petroleum ether, and (ii) with ether gave two different fractions.

(i) *Petroleum ether fraction*: The petroleum ether extract showed the presence of 5 spots by T.L.C. on silica gel. It was chromatographed on a column of silica gel to yield a total of 90 fractions of 20 ml each (cf. Table I). Each fraction was tested by T.L.C. and the fractions with the same product were combined.

TABLE I

No.	Fractions	Solvent	Substance
I	1—5	Petr. ether (60°–80°)	Dark coloured oily liquid
II	6—30	Petr. ether : benzene (80 : 20)	Single spot on T.L.C.
III	31—50	Petr. ether : benzene (50 : 50)	Single spot on T.L.C.
IV	51—70	Petr. ether : benzene (5 : 95)	Two spots on T.L.C.
V	71—80	Benzene	Nil
VI	81—90	Chloroform	Green substance.

The substance obtained from part II i.e., fractions 6–30 on crystallisation from methanol-chloroform gave a colourless product m.p. 68–70°

The substance obtained from part III i.e., fractions 31–50 on crystallisation from methanol-chloroform gave colourless crystals m.p. 136–38°; acetate m.p. 130–34° (cf. β -sitosterol m.p. 136–37°; acetate m.p. 134–35°). This has been identified as β -sitosterol by mixed m.p. and I.R. spectra with authentic sample of β -sitosterol

1. D. S. Rao, *Naturiss.*, 1965, 52(10), 262.

2. K. Leela and K. N. S. Sastry, *Leather Science* (Madras, India), 1964, 11(5), 186.

Part IV fractions 51-70 showed the presence of two spots by TLC. All attempts to separate the two products by crystallisation were unsuccessful and therefore this was transformed into acetate. The acetate on repeated crystallisations yielded colourless crystals (T.L.C. pure) of one of the substances and had m.p. 216-18° (cf. lupeol acetate m.p. 218°) and has been identified as lupeol acetate by superimposable I.R. spectra with authentic sample.

(ii) *Ether extract* : The ethereal extract on subsequent treatment gave a substance on crystallisation with methanol and had m.p. 237-40°.

(iii) *The residue* : The residue left over after the extraction of alcoholic extract with petroleum ether and ether on repeated crystallisations from various solvents gave a product m.p. 218-20° (dec.).

Thanks are due to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the award of a junior research fellowship to one of the authors (N.K.D.) and to the authorities of Shri G. S. Technological Institute, Indore for the facilities.

Department of Chemistry,
G.S. Technological Institute,
Indore-3.

Received January 21, 1969.